

Synthesis of 3,4(Benzo)-6,7-Naphthomorphan Derivatives

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Substituted-4-methyl-N-alkyl-quinolinium iodides (Ia~If) were condensed separately with α -chloromagnesium methyl naphthalene to get the corresponding 1,2-dihydroproducts (IIa~IIIf). Intermediates (IIa~IIIf) were cyclised with 85% H_3PO_4 to substituted 3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphans (IIIa~IIIIf) having an entirely new heterocyclic moiety. The structures were established through elemental and spectral studies.

6,7-BENZOMORPHANS, the most abbreviated form of morphine, were found to be most potent analgesics with less side effects. Replacement of benzene ring of 6,7-benzomorphan by naphthalene ring resulted in the formation of 6,7-naphthomorphans which were found to be powerful anticonvulsants and narcotic antagonists⁸. The present communication deals with the synthesis of some substituted 3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphans wherein the piperidine ring of 6,7-naphthomorphans is modified to tetrahydroquinoline ring starting from substituted-4-methyl quinolinium iodides (Ia~If) instead of alkyl pyridinium iodides, resulting in the additional fusion of benzene ring at positions 3 and 4 of 6,7-naphthomorphans. This would enable us to carry the comparative pharmacological activity of these compounds. Ia~If were condensed separately with α -chloromagnesium methyl naphthalene to get the corresponding 1,2-dihydro-products (IIa~IIIf, intermediates). Such intermediates have been generally found to be unstable^{4,5}. A small portions of these (IIa~IIIf) were treated with ethereal hydrogen chloride to get their respective hydrochlorides for structural elucidation. These were identified as 2-(1-naphthylmethyl)-N-alkyl or N-aralkyl-4-methyl-1,2-dihydro quinolines (IIa~IIIf) rearranging to the corresponding 2-(1-naphthylmethyl)-N-alkyl- or N-aralkyl-4-methyl quinolinium chlorides⁵. IIa~IIIf were separately cyclised with 85% H_3PO_4 when the corresponding cyclised products IIIa~IIIIf were obtained. The structures were established through elemental and spectral studies.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Spectral studies were done at chemical laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur. Nmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R12B spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. Microanalyses were done at CDRI, Lucknow. The values for elemental analysis, m.p. and % yields are given in Table 1.

4-Methyl-1-phenethyl-quinolinium iodide (Ia) :

4-Methyl-quinoline (4.29 g, 0.03M) was condensed with β -phenethyl iodide (6.96 g, 0.03M) in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Sl. No.	m.p. °C	% Yield
Ia	145	75.5
Ib	240	71.4
Ic	238	85.0
Id	175	80.0
Ie	148	68.0
If	187	83.9
IIa. HCl	103	50.16*
IIb. HCl	162	60.7*
IIc. HCl	113-114	41.0*
IId. HCl	103-5	37.0*
IIe. HCl	187	57.73*
IIIf. HCl	125	50.00*
IIIa. HCl	96.0	50.00
IIIf.	145	25.00
IIIc. HCl	150	40.00
IIId. HCl	125	41.00
IIIe.	165	35.00
IIIIf. HCl	118-20	40.00

* % Yields are given as 1,2-dihydrobases.

acetone (50 ml). It yielded 4-methyl-1-phenethyl-quinolinium iodide (Ia, 8.50 g) as yellow needles^{6,7}.

As above other N-substituted-4-methyl-quinolinium iodides (Ib~If) were also synthesised (cf. Table 1).

2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-1-phenethyl-4-methyl-quinolinium chloride (IIa.HCl) :

To a suspension of Ia (6.0 g, 0.016M) in dry ether (50 ml) ethereal solution of α -chloromagnesium methyl-naphthalene (α -chloro-methyl-naphthalene, 4.41 g, 0.025M, magnesium 0.60 g, 0.025M and ether 50 ml) was added within 15 min. The reaction mixture was stirred continuously for 2 hr at room temperature and for another 4 hr at 30-40°. The reaction mixture was treated in the usual manner⁸ and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Removal of solvent afforded a crude oily product which was distilled under reduced pressure (130-40°/0.3 mm) to yield IIa (3.12 g, 50.16%) as an oil. A small portion of it was converted to its hydrochloride (IIa. HCl, m.p. 103°) and the rest of the compound was subjected to cyclisation.

Other 1,2-dihydro products (IIb~IIIf) were also

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TABLE 2—NMR AND IR SPECTRAL DATA (CHEMICAL SHIFTS EXPRESSED IN δ ppm)

Sl. No.	Solvent used	Aromatic protons	-O-CH ₂	N-CH ₂	N-O-CH ₂	N-O-CH ₂ N-OH ₂	-CH ₂	-CH ₂	-CH-	-OCH ₂ /OH	IR ν cm ⁻¹
IIa.	HCl TFA	6.30-8.25(17H)	2.60(s)(3H)	—	—	4.80(t)(2H) 3.0(t)(2H)	—	4.25(s)(2H)	—	—	—
IIc.	HCl TFA	6.6-8.5(11H)	2.78(s)(3H)	4.4(s)(3H)	—	—	—	4.20(s)(2H)	—	3.85(s)(3H)	—
IIe.	HCl TFA	6.7-8.5(11H)	2.80(s)(3H)	—	1.15(t)(3H)	3.10(q)(2H)	—	4.25(s)(2H)	—	3.80(s)(3H)	—
IIf.	HCl TFA	6.50-8.2(16H)	2.75(s)(3H)	—	—	5.00(t)(2H) 3.20(t)(2H)	—	4.25(s)(2H)	—	3.90(s)(3H)	—
IIIa.	HCl CCl ₄	6.70-8.20(15H)	1.15(s)(3H)	—	—	2.3-3.40* (4H)	1.70(d)(2H)	2.3-3.40(2H)*	2.3-3.4* (1H)	—	—
IIIb.	CDCl ₃	6.70-8.2(10H)	1.30(s)(3H)	3.30(s)(3H)	—	—	—	3.5-3.85*(2H)	3.5-3.85* 1H at C ₁ & 1H at C ₆	—	—
IIIc.	HCl CDCl ₃	6.7-8.4 (9H)	1.3(s)(3H)	2.5-4.0* (3H)	—	—	1.85(d)(2H) at C ₆	2.5-4.0*(2H)	2.5-4.0* 1H at C ₁	4.25(1H)	1600 3400
IIId.	HCl TFA	6.8-8.4(9H)	1.27(s)(3H)	—	0.9(t)(3H)	3.0-4.0* (2H)	1.70(d)(2H) at C ₆	3.0-4.0*(2H)	3.0-4.0* 1H at C ₁	4.80(1H)	1610 3400
IIIe.	CDCl ₃	6.8-8.4(9H)	1.27(s)(3H)	—	0.9(t)(3H)	3.0-4.0* (4H)	1.75(d)(2H) at C ₆	3.0-4.0*(2H)	3.0-4.0* 1H at C ₁	4.8(1H)	1600 3400
IIIf.	HCl TFA	6.70-8.2(14H)	1.15(s)(3H)	—	—	2.25-3.30* (4H)	1.70(d)(2H) at C ₆	2.25-3.30*(2H)	2.25-3.30* 1H at C ₁	4.80(1H)	—

* A complicated pattern observed due to the presence of different type of protons.

synthesised by condensing α -chloromagnesium-methyl naphthalene with Ib~If separately. 1,2-Dihydro products (IIb~IIf) were also converted to their respective hydrochlorides IIb.HCl~IIf.HCl for structural elucidation (cf. Tables 1 and 2).

2-N-Phenethyl-5-methyl-3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan(IIIa) :

IIa (0.0075M) was immediately subjected to cyclisation at 150-60° with 85% H₃PO₄ for 48 hr. The cold reaction mixture was poured in cold ammoniacal water and extracted with chloroform. The solvent layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was distilled off when the crude cyclised product was obtained. It was distilled under reduced pressure (160-70°/0.1 mm) when an oily substance was obtained (IIIa, 1.36 g, 50%). A small portion of it was converted to its hydrochloride (IIIa.HCl, m.p. 96°). The purity of IIIa was ascertained through tlc using EtOH, EtOAc and HCOOH (6 : 2 : 2) as mobile phase (Rf=0.57).

On similar lines 1,2-dihydro products IIb~IIf were separately cyclised in 85% H₃PO₄ to get the corresponding 3,4 (benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphans (IIIb~IIIf) (cf. Table 1).

Discussion

Structural elucidation :

2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-4-methyl-N-alkyl or aralkyl-quinolinium chlorides (IIa.HCl~IIf. HCl) :

Elemental analyses were consistent with the molecular formulae assigned to IIa.HCl~IIf.HCl and the following definite structures were given on the basis of nmr spectral studies (cf. Table 2).

IIa. HCl : 2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-4-methyl-1-phenethyl-quinolinium chloride.

IIb. HCl : 2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-1,3,4-trimethyl-quinolinium chloride.

IIc. HCl : 2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-1,4-dimethyl-6-methoxy-quinolinium chloride.

IIId. HCl : 2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-1-ethyl-4-methyl-6-methoxy-quinolinium chloride.

IIe. HCl : 2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-1-propyl-4-methyl-6-methoxy quinolinium chloride.

IIIf. HCl : 2-(1-Naphthyl-methyl)-4-methyl-1-phenethyl-6-methoxy-quinolinium chloride.

2-N-Phenethyl-5-methyl-3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan(IIIa) :

On the basis of elemental analysis of hydrochloride salt of IIIa, the molecular formula was assigned as C₂₉H₂₇N.HCl. The nmr spectrum of liquid base in CCl₄ indicated the presence of fifteen aromatic protons in the range 6.70-8.20. There was a complicated pattern for seven protons in the region 2.30-3.40, a doublet for two protons and a singlet for three protons at 1.70 and 1.15 respectively. 3H singlet at 1.15 accounted for the presence of methyl group attached to quaternary carbon atom C₈ indicating thereby that the cyclisation had taken place at position 4 of quinoline ring. The presence of a doublet for two protons at 1.70 indicated the protons at C₆. A complicated pattern at 2.30-3.40 accounted for the presence of two protons at C₂ (benzylic) one proton at C₁ and four protons of two methylene groups of N-phenethyl group. On the basis of these observations the structure of IIIa was assigned as 2-N-phenethyl-5-methyl-3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan. Similarly the structures to IIIb~IIIf were assigned on the basis of nmr spectra as follows (cf. Table 2).

IIIb. 2,5,9-Trimethyl-3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan.

IIIc. 9'-Hydroxy-2,5-dimethyl-3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan.

IIId. 9'-Hydroxy-2-ethyl-5-methyl-3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan.

IIIe. 9'-Hydroxy-2-N-propyl-5-methyl (3,4-benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan.

III f. 9'-Hydroxy-2-N-phenethyl-5-methyl-3,4-(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphan.

It is observed in the 6,7-benzomorphan series that when methyl group at nitrogen is replaced by phenethyl group having methyl group at C₅ position, the analgesic potency increases many times¹⁰. The introduction of hydroxy group in benzene ring meta to quaternary carbon (C₅) also resulted in compounds having greater analgesic potency^{1,2,9}. The present communication is an attempt to study the mode of cyclisation of bulkier rings i.e., naphthalene ring at 6,7-positions having additional fusion of benzene ring at positions 3 and 4, this resulted in the formation of 3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphans (IIIa~III f) having different alkyl or analkyl groups at nitrogen. We have also introduced hydroxy group in the benzene ring. In 6,7-benzomorphan series 2'-hydroxy-2N-phenethyl-5,9-dimethyl-6,7-benzomorphan (phenazocine) is a clinically accepted drug¹⁰. So after getting success in the synthesis of 3,4(benzo)-6,7-naphthomorphans (IIIa~III f), we will now attempt to synthesise the phenazocine analogue of these compounds. The

synthesis of III b is an attempt to proceed in this direction.

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